

**ASSESSMENT OF CADMIUM EXCEEDANCE AND PHYSICOCHEMICAL
ANOMALIES IN FOUR URBAN DRAINS OF LUCKNOW: A DUAL-SEASON ICP-
MS AND MULTIVARIATE ANALYSIS**

SAKSHI VERMA¹, RAHUL VERMA¹, VIPPAN KAUR¹ & PRAMILA PANDEY^{2*}

SAKSHI VERMA¹ (Research Scholar, Department of Botany, University of Lucknow,
Lucknow-226007, India, Email id: skshivermaa7007@gmail.com)

RAHUL VERMA¹ (Research Associate, Department of Botany, University of Lucknow,
Lucknow-226007, India, Email- rahulvermark22@gmail.com)

VIPPAN KAUR¹ (Research Scholar, Department of Botany, University of Lucknow,
Lucknow-226007, India, Email id: vippanlmp007@gmail.com)

PRAMILA PANDEY² (Assistant Professor, Department of Botany, B.S.N.V. P.G.
College, Lucknow, India, Email- pramila28@gmail.com)

Corresponding author* Email: pramila28@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Wastewater discharge into surface waters poses environmental risks, and contaminates the surface water as well as ground water via leaching. Considering the heavy pollution load due to natural and anthropogenic activities, the Gomti River has been chosen to conduct this study. This study evaluated the physicochemical characteristics and heavy metal contamination in wastewater from four drainage sites in Lucknow district: Hanuman Setu, China Bazar, Nishat Ganj, and Jopling Road. Using Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectroscopy (ICP-MS) samples showed the difference concentration of heavy metals during monsoon season and winter season due to various reasons and the water sample hardness levels also vary in both seasons. All heavy metals (As, Pb, Mo, Cu, Ni, Cr) were within acceptable limits, except for cadmium (Cd), which exceeded WHO recommendations. The findings indicate that effluents are harmful for aquatic life and it need proper management and require treatment before discharge in water bodies.

Keywords: Wastewater, Physico-chemical parameters, Heavy metal, Plasma Mass spectroscopy, WHO.

1. INTRODUCTION

Water resources are increasingly limited, particularly in developing countries such as India. According to the Composite water management index report from India's Ministry of Jal Shakti and Ministry of Rural Development (NITI Aayog 2019), water availability per person is rapidly declining due to a combination of rapid socioeconomic development and

inadequate water consumption. In recent years, developing countries like India have seen a significant increase in wastewater discharge into the various water bodies and it also create a lot of problem due to open dumping in various cities, driven by rising population and rapid urbanization (Pirsaheb *et al.* 2014; Preisner 2020). During rapid urbanization and industrial development different types of harmful metals released from various waste; such as chromium (Cr), Lead (Pb), Arsenic (As) and mercury (Hg) are released into the various water bodies and soil ecosystem. These toxic substances can leach into the soil and ground water, ultimately it impacting water resources (Srinivasan & Reddy 2009) and create a big challenge for future generation. The high concentration of these heavy metals and the unchecked discharge of contaminated water by expanding industries are directly linked to heavy metal pollution in water bodies (Al-Mur *et al.* 2017). Heavy metals are classified as either essential or non-essential based on their biological effects on human being and different types of plants. Essential heavy metals (EHMs) are necessary for life, but excessive amounts can be harmful (Singh *et al.* 2011).

Blood haemoglobin contains the metals like iron (Fe) and cobalt (Co). Additionally, maintaining a healthy ratio of zinc (Zn) to copper (Cu) can enhance the human body's resistance against different diseases caused by various harmful substances (Taslina *et al.* 2022). However, non-essential heavy metals (NEHM) are generally considered harmful to living organisms, even at low doses, due to their lack of biological activity (Zhao *et al.* 2022; Abd Elnabi *et al.* 2023; Kim *et al.* 2019). One significant drawback of using without proper treatment of wastewater it may have various type of contaminants and these contaminants may harmful for human being as well as it affects the crops ecosystem because its accumulation (Singh *et al.* 2010).

The physicochemical characteristics of water, such as electrical conductivity (EC), pH, total dissolved solids (TDS), turbidity, hardness, and alkalinity are closely linked to various types of natural and anthropogenic activities. The primary sources of heavy metals in aquatic environments include agricultural herbicides, pesticides, insecticides and use of excess amount of manure and industrial wastewater. While water naturally contains trace amounts of heavy metals, elevated levels can lead to toxicity and negatively impact the aquatic ecosystem (Kotalova *et al.* 2020). Using recycled water for irrigation can allow the nutrients present to serve as a source of fertilizer. Under sewage effluent irrigation, soil microorganisms can demonstrate increased metabolic activity (Meli *et al.* 2002; Ramirez-Fuentes *et al.* 2002). In soils irrigated with wastewater, concentrations of total magnesium (Mg), mercury (Hg), molybdenum (Mo), calcium (Ca), copper (Cu), and chromium (Cr), as

well as available concentrations of lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), and copper (Cu), can increase significantly while remaining below harmful levels (Ramirez-Fuentes *et al.* 2002). Addressing the rising levels of pollution and the ongoing depletion of freshwater resources is an urgent necessity. Most of India's natural water resources are contaminated by the direct discharge of domestic and industrial wastewater that contains hazardous materials and pathogens. Although municipal wastewater treatment plants can effectively treat contaminated wastewater, challenges remain (Sharma *et al.* 2014; Sirisha *et al.* 2017; Kumar *et al.* 2019). Wastewater contains substantial amounts of both organic and inorganic nutrients.

Lucknow, the capital of Uttar Pradesh, is an oldest city in northern India, situated in the center of the state along the Gomati River. The city's drainage system suffers from poor management, resulting in frequent flooding and pollution of the Gomati River. Out of 28 drains in the area, 20 are clogged. Many of the drains in Lucknow are choked and untreated, which contributes to the pollution of other water bodies. Untreated waste from these drains continues to discharge into the Gomati River, exacerbating its pollution. There have been several efforts to prevent untreated waste from entering the Gomati River, including upgrading the sewage treatment system (STP). However, during the monsoon season, Lucknow frequently experiences waterlogging, primarily due to poor drainage congestion.

This study aims to measure various physicochemical parameters and trace metal concentrations at four drainage sites in Lucknow, located near the Gomati River. Based on our research, we have implemented specific procedures for sample collection, preservation, and storage to ensure accurate analysis of water parameters and heavy metal concentrations.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Study area

Lucknow city is located in the central part of the province and the capital of Uttar Pradesh. It is situated along both sides of the river Gomati- a tributary of the river Ganga. It lays between 26°30' to 27°10' North latitude and 80°30' to 81°13' East longitudes. It covers an area of 2544 sq. km and the area of the city is 310.104 sq km excluding cantonment area. The summers are hot and dry, lasting from March to June, followed by the monsoon season from July to September, and winters from November to February.

This study was conducted from four locations were selected to evaluate the physicochemical parameters and the concentration of heavy metals during the monsoon and

winter seasons. The sampling sites are as follows: (I) Hanuman Setu drain (II) China Bazar drain (III) Nishat Ganj drain (IV) Jopling Road drain.

Table- 1: Represents the GPS Map location of all sampling sites and MLD (GPS coordinates).

Sr. No.	State of India	Drains	Latitude	Longitude
1.	Uttar Pradesh	Hanuman Setu Drain	26.86056	80.93762
2.		China Bazar Drain	26.85809	80.99676
3.		Nishat Ganj Drain	26.87071	80.95731
4.		Jopling Road Drain	26.85306	80.95586

Figure- 1: Location of all chosen drainage sites on map (A), Hanuman Setu Drain (B), China Bazar Drain (C), Nishat Ganj Drain (D), Jopling Road Drain (E).

2.2. Sample collection and preparation

Four distinct sampling stations were selected based on identified pollution sources, labelled with S1, S2, S3, and S4. These locations are as follows: S1 is the Hanuman Setu drain, S2 is the China Bazar drain, S3 is the Nishat gang drain, and S4 is the Jopling road drain. Wastewater sample were collected for the analysis of physicochemical parameters, collected in 500 mL polystyrene bottles. It was transported on ice to the laboratory and stored at 4°C

until further use. Before collection, the bottles were properly washed and thoroughly rinsed several times with distilled water. Each sample was placed into two bottles: one non-acidified sample for other parameter testing and one acidified with 1 mL of 65% concentrated nitric acid to preserve trace elements.

2.3. Physicochemical Parameters:

The water samples were analyzed for physical and chemical parameters using standard methods.

2.3.1. pH

The pH was determined using a portable pH meter, which measures the concentration of H^+ ions in the sample. This instrument was calibrated with buffer solutions of pH 4.5, 7, and 9.8. To measure the pH, 50 mL of the water sample was taken in a beaker, and the glass electrode was immersed into the test sample (Sividu *et al.*, 2023).

2.3.2. Alkalinity

Alkalinity refers to the capacity of water to neutralize acids and reflects its buffer capacity, as water can absorb H^+ ions without a significant change in pH value. The sources of alkalinity in water or soil include carbonates, bicarbonates, and hydroxides. Alkalinity was determined using acid-base titration, with 0.02 N H_2SO_4 as the titrating agent. For the test, 50 mL of the water sample was placed in a conical flask, and 4-5 drops of phenolphthalein indicator were added. If a pink color developed, the sample was titrated with 0.02 N of H_2SO_4 until the pink color faded. Then, 1-2 drops of methyl orange indicator were added, and titration was continued until the color changed from yellow to orange. The burette reading was recorded at this point (Sividu *et al.*, 2023).

Calculation= $CaCO_3 - 50 \times N / 50 \times \text{ml of acid used} \times 1000 / \text{ml of sample used}$.

2.3.3. Hardness;

For the determine hardness in water, the EDTA titration method is employed. In this method, a 50 ml water sample is taken, and 2 ml of ammonia buffer is added, followed by a pinch of Eriochrome Black T (EBT), which initially gives a purple colour. After that, the sample is titrated with 0.01 M EDTA until it turns blue instead of purple (Sividu *et al.*, 2023). The formula for calculating total hardness (mg/L) as Calcium carbonate ($CaCO_3$) is: {Total Hardness (mg/L)} = {(A-B) \times 1000} / {mL of sample taken}

2.3.4. Total Dissolved Solids (TDS):

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) represent the total concentration of dissolve solids in water. The primary contributors to TDS are particles and sediments found in water, which can affect its odour and flavour. TDS is measured using an electrical conductivity meter. To conduct the

measurement, the instrument is turned on, and the probe is rinsed with distilled water. A water sample is then taken, and the probe/electrode is immersed in the sample to obtain a reading (Sividu *et al.*, 2023).

2.3.5. Electrical Conductivity (EC)

Electrical conductivity measures the ability of water to carry an electric current, which is influenced by the presence of dissolved solids and dissociated substances. Conductivity is quantified using a digital conductivity meter, expressed in micro siemens per centimetre ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$). Prior to measurement, the meter is calibrated using a 0.1 N KCl solution. The electrical conductivity indicates the total concentration of all biological and inorganic materials present in the water sample (Sividu *et al.*, 2023).

2.3.6. Chloride Concentration

Chloride concentration in a water sample is determined using Mohar's method. In this approach, silver nitrate (AgNO_3) is used to titrate with Cl^- ions, with potassium chromate serving as the indicator. During titration, when all Cl^- ions are removed, the color of the sample transitions from yellow to brick red (Sividu *et al.*, 2023). The formula for calculating chloride concentration (mg/L) is:

$$\text{Chloride (mg/L)} = (A-B) \times N \times 35.450 \times \frac{1000}{\text{mL of sample taken}}$$

Where A is the sample water measurement, and B is the distilled water measurement.

2.3.7. Turbidity

Turbidity refers to the presence of suspended solids or impurities in water, often caused by fine organic matter and microorganisms. The turbidity of a water sample is measured using a digital turbidity meter, which is calibrated with a 40 NTU solution prior to measurement. This 40 NTU solution is prepared using two reagents: hexamethylene tetraamine and hydrazine sulphate.

2.3.8. Metal Analysis Using ICP-MS

Polystyrene bottles were used to collect water samples. To preserve trace elements in pure form, one bottle of water samples was acidified with 1 milliliter of 65% concentrated nitric acid. The collected samples were then filtered through a 0.45 μm syringe filter designed for general particle filtration to remove any particulate matter. The samples were analyzed for heavy metals, including Chromium (Cr), Cadmium (Cd), Lead (Pb), Nickel (Ni), and Arsenic (As), using Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS). The concentration of different heavy metals at four drainage sites is expressed in parts per billion (ppb).

2.4. Statistical analysis

All results are presented as mean values from three replicates, accompanied by standard deviations. Additionally, Pearson correlation analysis was conducted for all studied parameters.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Physicochemical Parameters

3.1.1. pH:

The pH value is a crucial indicator of water quality and contamination levels in the watershed area. The pH impacts corrosion in wastewater treatment plant piping systems as well as the solubility of most metals in water. Therefore, it is essential to monitor pH closely during wastewater treatment processes (Messrouk *et al.*, 2014). The highest pH value was recorded at sampling Site 2 (8.12), which is the China Bazar drain during the rainy season. The pH values at all sampling sites fall within the acceptable range, indicating that there is no cause for concern. This study found that the pH value of wastewater during the rainy season is slightly alkaline, ranging from 6.56 (Nishat Ganj Drain) to 7.74 (Hanuman Setu Drain). In contrast, pH values during the winter season range from 7.59 (China Bazar Drain) to 8.15 (Jopling Road Drain). All drain water samples are within the permissible limit, as shown in Table- 2.

3.1.2. EC:

In terms of conductivity in various sampling sites, the highest value was recorded at Jopling Road Drain, measuring 1322 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$, while the lowest value of 1263 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$ was noted at China Bazar Drain during the rainy season. In the winter season, Jopling Road Drain again showed higher electrical conductivity at 1159 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$, whereas the lowest recorded value was 564.66 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$ at Hanuman Setu Drain site. This variation may be attributed to its relatively shallow depth, as electrical conductivity can be influenced by surface activities (Tables 2 and 3).

3.1.3. Hardness:

Regarding water hardness, the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) sets the permissible limit for drinking water hardness below 200 mg/l. However, there are no specific regulations for wastewater hardness. In this study, the maximum hardness value was observed at Site 2 (China Bazar Drain) during the monsoon season, while the minimum was recorded at Site 3 (Nishat Ganj Drain) also in the monsoon season (Tables 2 and 3). Except for Site 3 (Nishat Ganj Drain) during the monsoon season and Site 4 (Jopling Road Drain) in the winter season,

all hardness values exceeded the permissible limit. Specifically, the maximum hardness value of 441.33 mg/L was found in the waters of Site 2 (China Bazar Drain) during the monsoon, and the minimum value of 161.33 mg/L was at Site 3 (Nishat Ganj Drain). In the winter season, the highest hardness value was 334 mg/L was recorded at Site 3 (Nishat Ganj Drain), while the lowest value was 138.66 mg/L observed at Jopling Road Drain (Table 2).

3.1.4. Turbidity:

Turbidity ranges from 8 to 37.3 NTU. Higher turbidity affects the light penetration necessary for phytoplankton growth, which indirectly impacts aquatic life. Notably, the water from the Hanuman Setu Drain has the highest turbidity rating at 21.67 NTU. During the winter season, and at the site of China Bazar Drain recorded the lowest turbidity at 8.00 NTU. However, in the winter season, the China Bazar Drain reached its maximum turbidity at 37.3 NTU, while the Hanuman Setu Drain had the lowest at 28.6 NTU (Table 2).

3.1.5 Chloride:

Chloride in water exists as compounds such as NaCl, KCl, and CaCl₂. Humans rarely experience chloride toxicity, with the exception of certain conditions like congestive heart failure that affect sodium chloride metabolism (M. Tariq *et al.* 2020). Chloride is a crucial parameter for assessing water quality, with higher concentrations indicating greater organic pollution. During the monsoon season, the highest chloride concentration was recorded at Nishat Ganj Drain site and the value was 473.23 mg/L, while the lowest concentration was recorded in the China Bazar Drain at 176.66 mg/L (Table 2). In the winter season, the maximum chloride concentration was observed in the Jopling Road Drain at 859.7 mg/L, whereas the lowest was in the Hanuman Setu Drain at 359.8 mg/L. Notably, chloride concentration values in these drains are two to four times higher from the permissible limit

3.1.6. Alkalinity:

During the monsoon season, the highest alkalinity level (374.67 mg/L) was observed at Site 4 (Jopling Road Drain), while a lower concentration (141.33 mg/L) was recorded at Site 1 (Hanuman Setu Drain). During the winter, Site 2 (China Bazar Drain) had the highest alkalinity content (476.66 mg/L), whereas Site 1 (Hanuman Setu Drain) had the lowest concentration (49.33 mg/L). Among the four sites, only Sites 3 and 4 sites had alkalinity concentrations above the acceptable limit but below the permissible limit (Table 2).

3.1.7. TDS:

Excessive salinity can be detrimental to both humans and the environment; it may cause dehydration in animals and impart a laxative effect and unpleasant mineral flavour to water. Additionally, high salinity raises the osmotic pressure of soil water, leading to an increase in

respiration rates and ultimately reducing plant growth and productivity (Amic *et al.* 2018). The Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) levels varied between 1365 ppm and 1759 ppm during the rainy season. Site 4 (China Bazar Drain) had the highest TDS content (1759 ppm), while Site 1 (Hanuman Setu Drain) had the lowest value (1365 ppm). In the winter season, the maximum TDS level was observed at Jopling Road Drain, measuring 207 ppm, and the minimum was again recorded at Site 1 (Hanuman Setu Drain) at 1852 ppm (Tables 2 and 3).

After analyzing the results, it is clear that the values of various parameters in all the drain water samples—such as pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), alkalinity, and chlorides—fall within acceptable ranges. However, the hardness in all drains is within the permissible limits, except for the hardness of Site 1, which is the Hanuman Setu Drain; this exceeded the permissible limit during the monsoon season. Additionally, the turbidity levels in all samples during both seasons surpassed the permissible limits. When physicochemical parameters exceed allowable limits, it can lead to significant issues for the entire ecosystem.

Table- 2: Mean concentration of physicochemical parameters during rainy and winter seasons at Lucknow (at four sampling sites).

Sr. No.	Parameters	Hanuman Setu	China Bazar	Nishat Ganj	Jopling Road
		Drain (S1)	Drain (S2)	Drain (S3)	Drain (S4)
MONSOON SEASON					
1.	EC (µs/ppt)	1279.00±9.01	1263.33±3.51	1277.67±6.80	1322.33±2.51
2.	TDS (µs/ppt)	1365±34.12	1431±35.77	1417±35.42	1759±43.97
3.	pH	7.74±0.03	6.59±0.035	6.56±0.04	7.64±0.03
4.	Turbidity (NTU)	21.67±2.08	8.00±1.00	12.67±1.52	9.33±2.51
5.	Alkalinity (mg/L)	141.33±6.43	284±5.29	235.33±3.05	374.67±5.03
6.	Hardness (mg/L)	398.67±6.11	441.33±4.16	161.33±6.11	268.67±11.37
7.	Chlorides (mg/L)	269.9±30	176.56±15.27	473.23± 15.27	209.9±10

Sr. No.		WINTER SEASON			
1.	EC ($\mu\text{s/ppt}$)	564.66 \pm 5.50	637.66 \pm 9.47	640 \pm 5.56	1159.33 \pm 2.51
2.	TDS ($\mu\text{s/ppt}$)	1852.33 \pm 2.51	1704 \pm 4.58	1832.66 \pm 3.05	207.66 \pm 3.51
3.	pH	7.71 \pm 0.05	7.59 \pm 0.035	7.59 \pm 0.07	8.15 \pm 0.11
4.	Turbidity (NTU)	28.66 \pm 1.52	37.33 \pm 3.05	34 \pm 2.64	45 \pm 2.00
5.	Alkalinity	149.33 \pm 7.02	476.66 \pm 10.06	378 \pm 7.21	291.33 \pm 16.16
	(mg/L)				
6.	Hardness (mg/L)	305.33 \pm 11.01	301.33 \pm 3.05	334 \pm 10	138.66 \pm 1.71
7.	Chlorides	369.8 \pm 20	523.13 \pm 15.27	419.8 \pm 26.45	859.7 \pm 20
	(mg/L)				

3.2. Heavy metal concentration in wastewater

Concentrations of heavy metal in four sampling sites—S1, S2, S3, and S4 from the Lucknow region were analysed in this study. The concentrations of heavy metals at these sites were observed and are illustrated in Figures 2 and 3. The concentration of cadmium (Cd) at site S1 was 3.36 ppb, which is more than the 3 ppb WHO recommended limit. All other sites showed concentrations below the permissible limit, with site S1 recording the highest level of Cadmium during the winter season at Hanuman Setu Drain (Figure 3).

Copper (Cu) is essential for the synthesis of haemoglobin and enzymes in the human body. In this study, Copper concentrations were detected at all four sites (Chaoua *et al.*, 2019). Despite the relatively low levels of copper, the effluent from industrial areas may be a contributing source of the Copper found at these locations (Haftu & Kumar, 2020).

The highest concentration of Molybdenum was observed at sampling site S4, Jopling Road Drain, where it measured 7.10 ppb during the winter season. Conversely, the minimum concentration of Molybdenum (0.05 ppb) was also recorded at site S4, but during the rainy season.

In the rainy season samples, the greatest concentration of lead (2.23 ppb) was found at site S1. During the winter, site S3, Nishat Ganj Drain, had the lowest levels of lead at 0.43 ppb, while site S1 recorded the highest values at 1.01 ppb.

At 4.31 parts per billion, location S1, Hanuman Setu Drain, had the highest arsenic concentration. Furthermore, S1 had the higher concentration of arsenic (2.15 ppb) of any site, while S4 had the lowest value (1.14 ppb).

For Chromium, the highest value was recorded at site S4 and the value was 1.60 ppb, whereas the lowest concentration was observed at site S1, which was 1.32 ppb (Figure 2). Heavy metal concentration at different drainage sites in the rainy season.

According to the results, the levels of cadmium (Cd) exceed the permissible limits, while the concentrations of copper (Cu), chromium (Cr), lead (Pb), arsenic (As), and nickel (Ni) remain below acceptable levels. Notably, Cr and Ni were not detected in any of the four samples collected during the monsoon season, but both metals were present in the winter season at all four sites, although their concentrations were still below permissible limits.

Figure- 2: Heavy metal concentration at different drainage sites in rainy season.

The higher levels of heavy metals observed at these drainage sites can be attributed to the dense population in various parts of the city. Previous research has indicated that the water from these sites has negative effects on human health, rendering it unsuitable for agricultural use.

Biodegradation reactions are directly influenced by elevated levels of bio-organic substances, work effectively in conjunction with pH and temperature. A higher pH level may inhibit the chlorination of water (Ma *et al.*, 2020). A primary source of the increased heavy metal concentrations is the mixing of industrial effluents with wastewater systems (Nassef *et al.*, 2007). Regular use of phosphatic fertilizers containing cadmium is a major contributor in the leaching of cadmium into soil and water. Elevated cadmium levels could lead to serious

health hazards, including damage to organs, hypertension, and renal failure (Nassef *et al.*, 2007; Rajappa *et al.*, 2010). While nickel and chromium were absent in the monsoon season, they were detected in the winter season.

Figure- 3: Heavy metal concentration at different drainage sites in the winter season.

3.3. Pearson's correlation analysis:

3.3.1. Analysis between physicochemical parameters (Rainy season)

Table- 3 represents a correlation matrix of various water quality parameters, including pH, Alkalinity, TDS (Total Dissolved Solids), EC (Electrical Conductivity), Hardness, Turbidity, and Chloride.

Insights from the Correlation Matrix:

- Strong positive or negative correlations are indicated by values near 1 or -1, respectively, whilst weak or nonexistent correlations are suggested by values near 0.
- The pH and Turbidity ($r = 0.788167$) indicating the strong positive correlation that turbidity tends to increase as pH increases.
- TDS and EC ($r = -0.90959$) showing strong negative correlation means that as Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) increase the Electrical Conductivity (EC) tends to be also decrease.
- Alkalinity and Chloride ($r = 0.889148$) showing the strong positive relationship suggests that both parameters often increase together, making it useful to monitor one to infer changes in the other.

- Hardness indicates that if the value of hardness increases the pH rises. Conversely, Hardness and Alkalinity ($r = -0.56033$) demonstrate that hardness decreases when alkalinity increases.
- Turbidity and Chloride ($r = 0.735026$) correlation shows that both turbidity and chloride levels often increase together.

Table- 3: Pearson correlation coefficients between physicochemical parameters in all 4 drainage sites of Lucknow city in the rainy season

	<i>pH</i>	<i>Alkalinity</i>	<i>TDS</i>	<i>EC</i>	<i>Hardness</i>	<i>Turbidity</i>	<i>Chloride</i>
<i>pH</i>	1						
<i>Alkalinity</i>	-0.20214	1					
<i>TDS</i>	-0.11064	0.590126	1				
<i>EC</i>	0.301111	-0.27559	-0.90959	1			
<i>Hardness</i>	0.772736	-0.56033	0.064611	-0.12443	1		
<i>Turbidity</i>	0.788167	0.383013	0.450655	-0.13335	0.510074	1	
<i>Chloride</i>	0.267263	0.889148	0.501927	-0.09985	-0.2069	0.735026	1

3.3.2. Analysis between physicochemical parameters (winter season)

Alkalinity, total dissolved solids (TDS), electrical conductivity (EC), and chloride exhibit very high positive correlations with one another. This indicates that when one of these parameters increases, the others tend to increase as well. Turbidity is also strongly correlated with alkalinity, TDS, EC, and chloride ion concentration; although its correlations with these parameters are slightly lower than the correlations among the first four. While, on the other side the Hardness shows negative correlations with nearly all other parameters, most notably with turbidity (-0.79645) and chloride (-0.58309). The pH value displays moderate to high positive correlations with alkalinity, TDS, EC, turbidity, and chloride (all above 0.65) but a slightly negative correlation with hardness.

Table- 4: Provides the Pearson correlation coefficients between the physicochemical parameters across all four drainage sites in Lucknow city during the winter season.

	<i>pH</i>	<i>Alkalinity</i>	<i>TDS</i>	<i>EC</i>	<i>Hardness</i>	<i>Turbidity</i>	<i>Chloride</i>
<i>pH</i>	1						
<i>Alkalinity</i>	0.863	1					
<i>TDS</i>	0.858364	0.997436	1				
<i>EC</i>	0.870389	0.996642	0.999652	1			
<i>Hardness</i>	-0.07548	-0.52897	-0.50345	-0.48097	1		
<i>Turbidity</i>	0.654139	0.933486	0.918482	0.90864	-0.79645	1	
<i>Chloride</i>	0.842648	0.996373	0.988417	0.98615	-0.58309	0.955662	1

3.3.3. Analysis between Heavy Metal concentration (Rainy season)

Table 5 represents a correlation matrix for five elements: Cd, Pb, As, Cu, and Mo, measured during the rainy season. The table displays the correlation coefficients between each pair of elements: High positive correlations are observed between Cd and Mo (0.950169), Pb and Mo (0.871565), Pb and As (0.861154), indicating that these pairs exhibit similar type of behaviour. The only strong negative correlation is found between Cd and Cu (-0.23682), suggesting an inverse relationship between these elements. The diagonal values are all 1, reflecting each element's perfect correlation with itself. Other correlation values indicate moderate or weak relationships among the elements.

Table- 5: Pearson correlation coefficients among heavy metal concentrations at all four drainage sites in Lucknow city during the rainy season.

	<i>Cd</i>	<i>Pb</i>	<i>As</i>	<i>Cu</i>	<i>Mo</i>
<i>Cd</i>	1				
<i>Pb</i>	0.718372	1			
<i>As</i>	0.271911	0.861154	1		
<i>Cu</i>	-0.23682	0.444468	0.821624	1	
<i>Mo</i>	0.950169	0.871565	0.533677	0.076795	1

3.3.4. Analysis between Heavy Metal concentrations (Winter season):

Table 6 represents a correlation matrix that analyzes the relationships between seven heavy metals (Cd, Pb, As, Cu, Mo, Cr, Ni) during the winter season. This matrix displays the pair

wise correlation coefficients, demonstrating the strength of the linear relationship between the concentrations of each metal.

3.3.5. Key Trends in the Matrix

Cadmium (Cd) and Chromium (Cr) display a very strong negative correlation (-0.97879), indicating that when Cd levels increase, Cr levels tend to decrease dramatically. Copper (Cu) shows a strong positive correlation with Molybdenum (Mo) (0.9302650) and Cr (0.935364), suggesting that these metals tend to increase together. However, Cd and Cu demonstrate a strong negative correlation (-0.95441). Lead (Pb) generally has weak correlations with other metals, except for a moderate negative correlation with Arsenic (As) (-0.64349) and a small positive correlation with Mo (0.350420). Nickel (Ni) and Cr are also strongly negatively correlated (-0.85071), while Ni and Cd show a strong positive correlation (0.7302640).

4.0. CONCLUSION

This study assessed the physicochemical parameters of wastewater (including EC, TDS, alkalinity, hardness, chlorides, turbidity, and pH). Maximum results fell within permissible limits at all sampling sites, except for hardness at site S1 during the winter season. Heavy metal concentrations were examined at four locations, including Cd, Pb, As, Ni, Cr, Mo, and Cu. The levels of heavy metals at these sites were within permissible limits according to WHO standards, except for Cd at site S1, which was above the permissible limit and may pose public health concerns. Untreated wastewater presents a significant global problem, leading to various diseases and the pollution of other water sources. A major issue arising from untreated wastewater is the scarcity and shortage of clean water. According to the Water Management Index (NITI AAYOG), India has only 4% of the world's total water resources, of which only 3% is fresh water. Effective wastewater treatment could contribute to the development of a clean ecosystem. By products generated from wastewater treatment, like biogases and nutrients, can be utilized in agriculture, power plants, and other sectors. The essence of this study is to enhance wastewater treatment practices to reduce groundwater contamination and alleviate health concerns related to water pollution.

5.0. REFERENCES

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